

Stereochemical Assignment by Nmr Spectroscopy. Diels-Alder Adducts of *p*-Benzoquinone with Cyclic Dienes

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Nmr spectroscopy has been employed to demonstrate the stereochemistry of Diels-Alder adducts of *p*-benzoquinone with substituted anthracenes by transforming the mono adducts into bis adducts. Restricted rotation about N-CO bonds and a preferred *trans* arrangement has been proposed for the C(1)-diacetamido group in 1-diacetamidoanthracene-*p*-benzoquinone adduct. It has been observed that the spectral pattern may not be diagnostic in configurational assignment of bis adducts of *p*-benzoquinone with similar dienes but may provide valuable information about the adducts with dissimilar dienes.

DIELS-ALDER reaction of *p*-benzoquinone with 1- and 2-substituted anthracenes may lead to configurational isomers (*syn* and *anti*) depending on the steric and electronic effects of the substituents. Spectral data of the adducts particularly when only one isomer is formed may not provide convincing evidence regarding the geometry of the molecule. Stereochemistry of the Diels-Alder adducts of maleic anhydride with cyclic dienes has been successfully demonstrated² with the help of conformational analysis about N-N and N-C bonds through their *N*-imide derivatives. However, this technique could not be applied in case of *p*-benzoquinone-anthracene adducts. Nmr spectroscopy may not be very helpful in configurational assignments of bis adducts of *p*-benzoquinone with similar dienes due to the symmetrical nature of the molecules. In this communication we report the introduction of a dissimilar diene to *p*-benzoquinone mono adducts and its potentiality as a probe in the configurational assignments. For this purpose, compounds (1-10) were prepared and were characterized by elemental analyses and spectral data (Tables 1-3).

- 1 $R_1 = \text{NAC}_2, R_2 = \text{H}$
 2 $R_1 = \text{H}, R_2 = \text{NAC}_2$
 3 $R_1 = \text{H}, R_2 = \text{OH}$
 4 $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}$

- 6
 7 $R_1 = \text{NAC}_2, R_2 = \text{H}$
 8 $R_1 = \text{H}, R_2 = \text{NAC}_2$
 9 $R_1 = \text{H}, R_2 = \text{OH}$
 10 $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}$

Results and Discussion

Pmr spectrum of Diels-Alder (DA) adduct of 1-diacetamidoanthracene and *p*-benzoquinone (1) exhibits two singlets at δ 1.68 and 2.56 each of 3H intensity for the two acetyls, along with other resonances (Table 1). The position of the acetyl resonances and their internal separation ($\Delta\delta = 1$ ppm) in compound 1 are very much similar to that of the *anti* isomer of 1-diacetamidoanthracene-maleic anhydride adduct³, suggesting for the *anti* configuration of the adduct 1. In case of *syn* configuration one of the olefinic protons would have been influenced by *N*-diacetamido group but a sharp singlet (2H) at δ 6.40 further suggests *anti* configuration.

The conformational analysis about N-CO bonds of 1-*N*-diacetamido group in 1 has proved to be interesting. In 1-diacetamidoanthracene and related system³ the appearance of C(1)-N(COCH₃)₂ as a singlet provides evidence for the magnetic equivalence of the two acetyls. Hindered rotation³ about C(1)-N bond is evident in such compounds due to the interaction of C(9) hydrogen with the C(1) substituents and free rotation about N-CO

bonds may render the acetyls to be magnetically equivalent. In compound **1** the appearance of two acetyl resonances at δ 1.78 and 2.78 must emerge from a preferred conformation about N-CO bonds with *trans* arrangement* like **11** or **12**. The shielding parameter (0.25 ppm) of C-9 proton with respect to C-10 proton could be exploited to distinguish between the two conformers **11** and **12**. Molecular models show that in **12**, C-9 proton falls in the shielding zone of C=O and the acetylmethyl (MeB) would undergo a diamagnetic shift since it lies towards the benzo ring. Conformer **12** thus accounts for both the shielding of C-9 proton and for the internal chemical shift of the two acetylmethyls.

^{13}C nmr spectrum of compound **1** has further provided additional evidence in support of the preferred *trans* arrangement of 1-*N*-diacetamido group. The spectrum exhibits resonances at δ 26.13 and 27.11 (acetylmethyl carbons), 43.62 and 47.62 (C-9 and C-10), 48.20 and 48.70 (C- α and C- β), 173.23 and 173.19 (amide carbonyl carbons) and 194.60 and 195.03 for the carbonyl carbons of cyclohexanedione moiety. ^{13}C nmr spectrum of *p*-benzoquinone-anthracene adduct (**4**) exhibits resonances at δ 48.92 (C-9 and C-10), 49.12 (C- α and C- β) and 194.03 (carbonyl carbons). A considerable shielding (5 ppm) of C-9 resonance in **1** would not be expected through bond interactions but may be due to crowding effect or 'field effect' (through space effect) of the substituent⁵. The shielding parameter (~ 1 ppm) between two methyl carbons in **1** suggests that the shielding is not caused by methyl group⁶ in **11** but likely through space effect of the carbonyl group in **12**. The appearance of the two amide carbonyl carbons at δ 172.03 and 173.19 supports the proposed preferred conformation and restricted rotation about N-CO bonds.

2-Diacetamidoanthracene and *p*-benzoquinone gave only one DA adduct. The appearance of the acetyl resonances at the normal position as a singlet in the pmr spectrum of the adduct **2** (Table 1)

indicate free rotation about N-CO bonds. It is not evident from the spectral data whether the adduct is *syn* or *anti*, though on theoretical grounds one would expect the adduct to be *anti*. ^{13}C nmr spectrum of compound **2** exhibits resonances at δ 26.75 (acetylmethyl carbons), 48.98 and 48.67 (C-9 and C-10), 49.01 (C- α and C- β), 173.25 (amide carbonyl carbons) and 194.72 (carbonyl carbons of the cyclohexanedione moiety). ^{13}C spectrum **2** thus indicates free rotation about N-CO bonds of the diacetamido group but does not provide any convincing clue about its configuration.

2-Methylantracene with *p*-benzoquinone gave an adduct (**3**), m.p. 204-5°. The spectral pattern (Table 1) does not provide any definite evidence about its geometry but the dibromo product (**5**) exhibits a singlet (3H) at δ 2.26 for (CH₃), a broad singlet (2H) at 3.60 (C- α and C- β protons) and AB quartet centred at 4.4 (CHBr methine protons), two broad singlets at 4.95 and 5.03 (each 1H) for C-9 and C-10 protons along with a multiplet (7H) at 7.3 for the cage-aromatic protons. Spectral studies of some brominated products have shown⁷ CHBr methine protons to be magnetically non-equivalent in *trans* addition of bromine to the olefinic bond. Thus an AB quartet in **5** suggests *trans* addition and the structure could be proposed as **14** where cyclohexanedione ring has somewhat a chair type conformation with the bromine atoms in *trans* diaxial orientation. The strong absorption⁸ at 1720 cm⁻¹ in the ir spectrum for carbonyl stretching supports the diaxial nature of the bromine atoms. Moreover, from the magnetic non-equivalence of C-9 and C-10 protons in **5**, it could be reasonably proposed that one of the carbonyls may be twisted below to cause deshielding of C-9 proton. The unaffected methyl resonance in **5** suggests *anti* configuration of the adduct.

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A bis DA adduct (**6**) of cyclopentadiene (2 mol) and *p*-benzoquinone (1 mol), m.p. 155° was obtained⁹.

TABLE I—NMR (60 MHz) SPECTRAL DATA* (δ ppm) OF COMPOUNDS 1-4

Compd. no.	R ₁ /R ₂	$\alpha + \beta$	9+10	Olefine	Cage-aromatic
1	1.68 (s, 3H) 2.56 (s, 3H)	3.02 (t, 2H)	4.61 (bs, 1H) 4.85 (bs, 1H)	6.40 (s, 2H)	7.33 (m, 7H)
2	2.18 (s, 6H)	3.20 (t, 2H)	4.97 (bs, 2H)	6.43 (s, 2H)	7.0-7.60 (m, 7H)
3	2.25 (s, 3H)	3.13 (t, 2H)	4.86 (bs, 2H)	6.46 (s, 2H)	7.15 (m, 7H)
4	—	3.15 (t, 2H)	4.92 (t, 2H)	6.38 (s, 2H)	7.30 (m, 8H)

* s=singlet, t=triplet, m=multiplet, bs=broad singlet.

TABLE 2—NMR (60 MHz) SPECTRAL DATA* (δ ppm) OF COMPOUNDS 7-10

Compd. no.	7'-CH ₂	R' ₁ +R' ₂	2'+3'	1'+4'	$\alpha + \beta$	9+10	5'+6'	Cage-aromatic
8	AB quartet, 2H, J_{AB} 9.1 Hz, A 1.39, B 1.05	1.70 (s, 3H) 2.63 (s, 3H)	2.40 (m, 2H)	2.73 (t, 2H)	3.23 (t, 2H)	4.60 (m, 1H) 4.83 (m, 1H)	6.12 (t, 2H)	7.33 (m, 7H)
	AB quartet, 2H, J_{AB} 9.0 Hz, A 1.36, B 1.03	2.24 (s, 6H)	2.41 (m, 2H)	2.83 (m, 2H)	3.27 (m, 2H)	4.76 (bs, 2H)	6.1 (t, 2H)	7.33 (m, 7H)
9	AB quartet, 2H, J_{AB} 9.2 Hz, A 1.31, B 0.98	2.28 (s, 3H)	2.35 (m, 2H)	2.75 (bs, 2H)	3.25 (m, 2H)	4.66 (bs, 2H)	6.1 (t, 2H)	7.16 (m, 7H)
10	AB quartet, 2H, J_{AB} 9.0 Hz, A 1.29, B 0.95	—	2.33 (m, 2H)	2.80 (t, 2H)	3.23 (t, 2H)	4.66 (t, 2H)	6.03 (t, 2H)	7.25 (m, 8H)

* Abbreviation as in Table 1.

Pmr spectrum of **6** exhibits an AB quartet (4H, A δ 1.49, B δ 1.39, J_{AB} 9Hz, 7 and 7'-CH₂), a triplet (4H) at δ 2.90 (1, 4, 1' and 4'-H), a triplet (4H) at 3.42 (2, 3, 2' and 3'-H) and a triplet 4(H) at 6.22 (5, 6, 5' and 6'-H). The spectral pattern of compound **6** depicts a symmetrical geometry of the molecule. It is also evident from molecular models that only *endo-endo* or *exo-exo* configuration would satisfy the condition of symmetry in the molecule. The possibility of *exo-exo* configuration may be excluded by considering the usual pronounced preference for *endo* kinetic control in Diels-Alder reaction¹⁰ and the preference of **14** over the other possible *endo-endo* configuration **15** is expected on steric grounds. The observed spectral pattern would, therefore, favour the *endo-endo* configuration (**14**) which is in agreement¹¹ with the earlier proposed structure. It may be pointed out that the spectral pattern of the adduct as such does not rule out the possibility of other symmetrical structures.

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Adduct **1** undergoes further Diels-Alder reaction with cyclopentadiene to form a bis adduct (**7**) in almost quantitative yield. Considering the *cis* fusion of bicycloheptene nucleus in the bis adduct, the cyclopentadiene may add *syn* or *anti* with respect to

the anthracene moiety. On steric grounds the *anti* addition would be the most probable. Diamagnetic shift of 2', 3' proton resonances in **7** (Table 3)

TABLE 3—M.p., ELEMENTAL ANALYSES AND CHARACTERISTIC IR PEAKS

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		ν_{max}^* cm ⁻¹
		C	H	
1	193-194	74.60	5.10	1720s, 1680s, 1600w
		(74.79)	(4.97)	
2	218-219	74.50	5.00	1725s, 1680s, 1600w
		(74.79)	(4.97)	
3	204-205	83.70	5.30	1680s, 1600w
		(83.98)	(5.97)	
4	235-236	83.70	5.10	1680s, 1590w, 1580w
		(83.90)	(4.93)	
5	148-150	54.55	3.62	1720s, 1600w, 1380m
		(54.81)	(3.50)	
6	154-155	80.00	6.48	1680s, 1480w
		(79.97)	(6.71)	
7	191-195	77.20	5.65	1720s, 1680w, 1660w, 1580w
		(77.14)	(5.58)	
8	181-182	77.00	5.60	1720s, 1690s, 1660w
		(77.14)	(5.58)	
9	164-165	85.00	6.10	1700s, 1600w
		(85.22)	(6.05)	
10	185-186	85.12	5.65	1700s, 1485m
		(85.20)	(5.72)	

* m=medium, s=strong and w=weak.

further supports the *anti* addition. In case of *syn* addition, 2', 3' protons would be on the opposite side of the benzo ring, while in *anti* addition, these protons would fall in the shielding zone of the benzo ring. In *anti* addition and assuming a boat conformation of the central cyclohexanone ring, two possibilities may arise, the bicycloheptene moiety may be *endo* (**16**) or *exo* (**17**). From mechanistic point of view¹⁰ of Diels-Alder reaction the *endo* configuration has been proposed. Further, this is supported by comparatively large chemical shift difference (0.34 ppm) between the two 7'-methylene protons in **7** than in **6**, since in *endo* configuration (**16**) one of the methylene protons would be influenced by the anisotropy effect of benzo ring

of anthracene moiety. So, the configuration of the bis adduct may be proposed as **16**. Magnetic non-equivalence of C-9 and C-10 protons and positions of the two acetyl resonances of **7** are almost same as in **1**, indicating no conformational change in the diacetamido group due to the formation of bis adduct. In case of *syn* configuration the resonance of the acetylmethyl would certainly have been influenced by the formation of bis adduct. The configurational assignment of bis adduct has, therefore, strongly supported the *anti* configuration of the mono adduct (**1**).

The spectral patterns of the bis adducts (**8-10**) (Table 3) suggest similar configuration as in **1**. Moreover, the formation of bis adduct does not influence the resonances of the substituents in **8** and **9**, thereby, supporting for the *anti* configuration of the mono adducts.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. Nmr spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 with TMS as an internal reference on a Varian A-60D spectrometer at 45° . ^{13}C nmr spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer CFT-20 spectrometer. Ir spectra were recorded in Nujol mull on a Perkin-Elmer 257 spectrophotometer. Melting points, chemical analyses and characteristic ir bands of the compounds are given in Table 3.

Substituted anthracenes: 1-Amino-, 2-amino- and 2-methylantracenes were prepared by the reduction of their corresponding anthraquinone derivatives by zinc dust and alkali^{1,2}. 1-Aminoanthracene was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. $126-27^\circ$; 2-aminoanthracene from toluene, m.p. $237-39^\circ$; and 2-methylantracene from acetone, m.p. $204-6^\circ$.

1- and 2-Diacetamidoanthracenes: Compounds were prepared by refluxing the corresponding aminoanthracene with an excess acetic anhydride for about 6 h. 1-Diacetamidoanthracene was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. $239-41^\circ$.

DA adducts of p-benzoquinone and substituted anthracenes (1-4): These were obtained¹³ by refluxing the corresponding anthracene and its derivatives with p-benzoquinone in equimolar proportion in dry xylene for 1 h. The products were recrystallised from benzene.

2-Methylantracene-p-benzoquinone adduct dibromide (5): Equimolar amount of bromine in dry chloroform (10 ml) was added dropwise to the stirred solution of the adduct **3** (0.2 g) in chloroform (15 ml) over a period of 2 h. On removal of solvent under reduced pressure a solid material was obtained. It was recrystallised from chloroform.

Bis-cyclopentadiene-p-benzoquinone adduct (6): **1** was obtained by stirring freshly distilled cyclopentadiene (0.43 ml) and p-benzoquinone (0.52 g) in dry benzene (15 ml) at 5° for about 6 h. After removing the solvent under reduced pressure a white solid material was obtained which on recrystallisation from ethanol gave prismatic crystals.

Anthracene-p-benzoquinone-cyclopentadiene DA adducts (7-10): These bis adducts were prepared by stirring the corresponding mono adduct with freshly distilled cyclopentadiene in equimolar quantity in dry benzene at 10° for 12 h. After removing the solvent under reduced pressure, the products obtained were recrystallised from ethanol.

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